

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

IMPROVING THE RECIPES OF EXTRUDED SORYZ MIXES USING WHEAT GERM

Iusan L.

*Doctor of Technical Sciences, Associate Professor,
ORCID ID <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4028-221X>
Scientific and Practical Institute of Horticulture,
Viticulture and Food Technologies in Chisinau,
Republic of Moldova*

ABSTRACT

Daily nutrition is one of the most important factors that directly affect human health. To have a positive effect on the organism in the food necessary to be combined optimally fats, proteins and carbohydrates.

Maintaining the body in the normal state - means maintaining the necessary balance between free radicals and antioxidant forces, the role played by antioxidants.

Therefore, it is necessary to nourish and sustain the organism with the necessary nutrients. The basis of the food pyramid is food obtained from cereals. Creating cereal foods with a higher content of biologically active compounds will allow the control of the aging process in the human body.

Keywords: Soryz, extrusion, cereal mixes, wheat germ.

Introduction

Pollution of nature significantly affects the quality and longevity of a contemporary people.

The daily diet is one of the most important factors that directly affects human health.

Questions related to "healthy eating" are worried any person who wants to get not only pleasure from food, but also benefits. To have a positive effect on the organism in the food necessary to be combined optimally fats, proteins and carbohydrates. You also need vitamins and minerals.

Maintaining the body in the normal state - means maintaining the necessary balance between free radicals and antioxidant forces, the role played by antioxidants.

Investigation by modern scientists has shown that antioxidants help prevent many diseases, such as myocardial infarction, hypertension and stroke.

The body has a system of antioxidant protection, which is divided into primary enzymes (antioxidants - enzymes) and secondary (antioxidants - vitamins A, E, C). This system works from birth and throughout the life, gradually weakens over the years. Consequently, there is a need to feed and support it. Wheat germ, rich in vitamins E and A, can be used as antioxidants.

The basis of the food pyramid is food obtained from cereals. It is necessary to include in the daily diet: cereals, cereals and muesli, which are obtained from whole grain flour. They are rich in carbohydrates and provide our body with energy.

The creation of products from cereals with a high content of biologically active substances will allow controlling the aging processes in the human body.

Materials and methods

The Scientific and Practical Institute of Horticulture, Viticulture and Food Technologies conducts scientific research to expand the range of products from soryz.

This problem is solved by a process such as extrusion. The extrusion process allows you to obtain a product with the desired properties, which allows you to expand the range of extruded products.

Currently, much attention is paid to a balanced diet, healthy foods are added to the daily diet. To provide the body with vitamins, trace elements and other nutrients, especially in winter, when there are some vegetables and fruits, it is recommended to use wheat germ in the diet.

The germs formed as by-products during the grinding of cereals and have special nutritional characteristics, taking into account the specific chemical composition [3,4].

Cereal germs are characterized by a increased content of B vitamins and vitamin E. They are rich in choline and betaine, P, K, Ca, Fe, Zn and other minerals.

Germs can be considered a source of protein in food, the content of this component is higher than in flour (17-35%). These proteins have a more balanced spectrum of amino acids (close to reference value), at the same time, while flour and cereals contain proteins with an unbalanced composition of essential amino acids. This aspect is important because the quality of proteins affects the formation of antibodies, brain development, physical and intellectual performance.

Germ lipids are triglycerides rich in polyunsaturated fatty acids, especially linoleic acid. Also phospholipids are important (phosphatidylethanolamine, phosphatidylcholine, phosphatidylinositol), which fight with atherosclerosis by inhibiting the absorption of cholesterol and preventing its deposition on the walls of blood vessels.

Wheat germs are also rich in phytosterols (β -sitosterol, stigmasterin), the main biological effect of which is to reduce level of cholesterol.

Through to the content of vitamins, germs can be considered a real natural multivitamins. High level of tocopherols are involved in the prevention of cardiovascular diseases, lowering level of cholesterol, preventing the accumulation of free radicals.

Due to its biological and educational potential, wheat germ is a valuable raw material for obtaining products that have a beneficial effect on human health [5].

In the UK, USA, Germany, wheat germ is used for the production of food additives that are added to milk, cream, desserts, cocktails and other products, as well as

in cosmetology in the production of creams, enriching them with vitamin E.

A grain of wheat consists of several components, each of which has a different chemical composition and is responsible for a specific physiological function in the process of growth and development. Table 1 shows the biochemical composition of wheat grain [6].

Table 1.

Biochemical composition of wheat grain and its components

Components of grain	Weight, g	Starch	Proteins	Carbohydrates	Fats	Pentosans	Cellulose	Ash
		%						
Grain	100	66,0	16,0	3,0	2,0	7,0	2,0	1,9
Pericarp	6 -8	-	4,0	1,0	0,5	47,0	2,0	4,0
Aleurone layer	5-9	-	35,0	6,0	9,0	25,0	15,0	10
Endosperm	78-84	80	14,0	2,3	0,7	1,5	0,1	0,4
Germ	2-3	-	35,0	25,0	15,0	15,0	2,5	5,0

In the food ration wheat grains are a source of carbohydrates and proteins. In the processing of cereals, the endosperm is mainly used for flour production

Wheat germ is a part of the grain from which a new plant grows. Cells of endosperm, as well as embryos, retain their vital activity even after storage, their biochemical composition is presented in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2.

The content of amino acids in grain and its components (% of total nitrogen)

Amino acids	Grain		Endosperm powdery body (white flour)		Wheat germs	
	Variation	Average	Variation	Average	Variation	Average
Arginine	2,8-4,8	4,2	3,1-3,9	3,3	6,0-6,9	6,4
Cytidine	1,4-2,2	1,9	1,5 -2,2	2,0	2,1- 2,5	2,3
Lysine	2,2 -2,9	2,5	1,9 -2,3	2,1	5,4-6,8	5,6
Tyrosine	3,8 – 4,8	4,0	3,8	3,8	3,8	3,8
Tryptophan	0,8 – 1,3	1,0	0,8 – 1,1	1,0	0,9 – 1,0	1,0
Cysteine	1,0 -2,0	1,9	1,9-4,5	2,2	0,6-1,4	1,0
Phenylalanine	3,7 – 5,7	5,1	5,5 -5,6	5,5	2,5 -4,2	3,8
Methionine	1,0 -2,5	1,3	1,0- 3,0	1,8	1,3-2,0	1,8
Threonine	2,5 – 3,2	2,8	2,5- 2,7	2,6	3,8-6,3	4,2
Leucine	5,8 – 8,3	6,2	7,5 -12,6	10,0	6,7-7,4	7,0
Isoleucine	3,1 – 4,0	3,6	3,5-3,9	3,7	2,9-5,2	3,2
Valin	3,6 - 4,8	4,2	3,4 -4,2	3,8	3,4-5,1	4,2
Glycine	-	-	7,2	7,2	-	-

In terms of chemical composition and nutritional value, wheat germ proteins significantly differ from endosperm proteins. According to their physicochemical

and physiological properties, they can be compared with proteins of animal origin - proteins of eggs, milk, beef [2, 11].

Table 3.

The content of vitamins in wheat grain and its components (in mg/100 g of dry matter)

Vitamins	Components of wheat grain	Variation	Average
Vitamin B1 (thiamine)	Endosperm powdery body (white flour)	0,07-0,13	0,09
	Germ	0,42-2,43	1,9
Vitamin B2 (riboflavin)	Endosperm powdery body (white flour)	0,03-0,07	0,05
	Germ	0,97-1,28	1,10
Vitamin PP (nicotinic acid)	Endosperm powdery body (white flour)	0,7-1,9	1,3
	Germ	3,4-9,1	6,4
Vitamin B6 (pyridoxine)	Endosperm powdery body (white flour)	0,12-0,22	0,17
	Germ	0,96-1,36	1,25
Provitamin D2 (ergosterol)	Endosperm powdery body (white flour)	0,08	0,08
	Germ	1,2	1,2
Provitamin A (β -carotene)	Endosperm powdery body (white flour)	следы	следы
	Germ	0,60	0,60
Vitamin E (tocopherol)	Endosperm powdery body (white flour)	0,03	0,03
	Germ	15,84	15,84
P-aminobenzoic acid	Endosperm powdery body (white flour)	0,6	0,6
	Germ	1,8	1,8

Wheat germ contains a lot of fat-soluble vitamins.

Fig. 1. Wheat germ samples

According to bibliographic sources [7-9], the use of wheat germ has the following effects:

- increases the resistance of the human body to the action of various factors, tones the muscular system;
- helps slow down the aging process and is recommended as a dietary supplement for the elderly.

Vitamin E is also able to prevent rancidity of fats as a result of oxidation, thus preventing damage caused by free radicals.

The role of vitamin A is to stimulate growth, promote the processes of protecting the skin, mucous

membranes from infections and adapting vision to darkness.

Results and discussions

The recipes were calculated based on the content of vitamins E and A in wheat germ.

By Government Decree[1], the daily dose required by the human body is 800 mg of vitamin A, and 12 mg of vitamin E. Usually the amount of added vitamins is 15% of the recommended daily dose.

Thus, the recipes of extruded products, presented in Table 4, were developed.

Table 4.

Recipes of extruded products from soryz with the addition of biologically active substances

Name of the raw material	Nr. 1	Nr. 2	Nr. 3	Nr. 4
1. Soryz	60	65	70	80
2. Corn grits	20	-	30	-
3. Buckwheat grain	-	15	-	20
4. Wheat germ	20	20	-	-

The basis of the methodological approach to the production of enriched food products with biologically active substances (BAS) includes the optimization of food systems by combining raw materials and the technology of its production with the technological, preventive and chemical properties of the food additive.

In the EU, the use of food additives is based on Directive 89/107CEE. In accordance with this Directive, three other specific directives on sweeteners (Directive 94/35 CE), colours (Directive 94/36 CE) and food additives (Directive 95/2 CE) have been developed and approved by the European Parliament.

Fig.2 Pilot installation of the Extruder-150

Enrichment of food products with wheat germ, containing a large amount of biologically active substances (vitamin A, vitamin E and polyunsaturated fatty acids), will increase the resistance of products to oxidative factors. And this in turn increased the shelf life and biological value of food products, especially those intended for the younger generation.

The production of a pilot batch of extruded products with the addition of wheat germ was carried out at the company "Policom Prim" SRL, on a single-screw extruder E-150.

Fig.3 Sample of extruded products with the addition of wheat germ

The technological process of manufacturing of samples of extruded products consists of several stages, namely: preparation of raw materials; moisturizing cereals; extrusion; drying; cooling of extrudate and packaging of the product.

The extruded products were analyzed according to the following physico-chemical parameters:

- humidity of extruded products, %;
- water retention coefficient,
- wetting coefficient;
- specific bulk weight, g/cm³;
- expansion coefficient.

The physico-chemical parameters of extruded products with the addition of wheat germ are presented in Table 5.

Table 5.

The physico-chemical parameters of extruded products with the addition of wheat germ

№	Name of extruded products	Humidity, %	Water retention coefficient	Wetting coefficient		Specific bulk weight, g/cm ³	Expansion coefficient
				30 min at 19-22 °C	5 min at 30°C		
1	Extrudate of soryz and corn grits	6,40	4,07	5,63	4,80	0,44	3,6
2	Extrudate of soryz, corn grits and wheat germ	6,96	4,06	5,00	5,15	0,49	3,3
3	Extrudate of soryz and buckwheat grains	6,30	4,20	5,41	4,15	0,44	3,5
4	Extrudate from soryz, buckwheat grains and wheat germ	6,60	3,69	4,93	3,96	0,51	3,1

Based on the data in Table 5, we note that the humidity of the extruded products is 6.3 - 6.96%. The addition of wheat germ to the extrudate significantly affected the changes in physico-chemical parameters:

- the expansion coefficient of extruded products decreased by 10% and is 3.1 - 3.3%, which negatively affected the structure of the extrudate;
- specific bulk weight increased by 15% and is 0.48 - 0.57 g/cm²;
- the wetting coefficient of extruded products decreases and is 4.93 - 5.0 at 20 °C and, respectively, 3.96 - 5.15 at 30 °C.

To establish the shelf life, experimental samples of extruded products with the addition of wheat germ were stored for 6 months of storage.

The results of microbiological analyses reflect the following: during storage for 6 months, microbiological indicators did not exceed acceptable indicators and corresponded to sanitary standards.

Conclusions

1. Based on the conducted research, namely the establishment of the biological value of wheat germ, an experimental batch of extruded products from soryz, corn grits, buckwheat grains and wheat germ was made.
2. The addition of wheat germ was made based on the content of vitamins E and A. The amount of added vitamins is 15% of the recommended daily dose.
3. The physicochemical and microbiological parameters of extruded products with the addition of wheat germ were determined.

References

1. Regulamentul sanitar privind mențiunile nutriționale și de sănătate înscrise pe produsele alimentare, aprobat prin Hotărârea Guvernului Republicii Moldova nr. 196 din 25.03.2011

2. Нечаев А.П., Траубенберг С.Е., Кочеткова А.А. Пищевая химия: - 2-е издание, переработанное и исправленное. - СПб.: ГИОРД, 2003.-640 с.

3. Gast K., Jungfer M., Saure C., Brunner G. Purification of tocochromanols from edible oil. *J. Supercrit. Fluids*, 2005, 34.N1, pp. 17 -25.

4. ТУ 8-22-64-89 Пшеничные зародышевые хлопья пищевого назначения.

5. Козырьков С.Ю. Новые направления в обеспечении населения США продуктами питания, - М., АгроНИТИ пищепром, 1989, вып. 7.

6. Семёнов В.М., Ярош А.М.. Метод определения антиокислительной активности биологического материала / Украинский биохимический журнал. -1985.-т.57.-с.50-52.

7. Malero Gomez. A., Martinez De La Ossa E.(Dep. Of Chem. Engin., Food tehnol. and Enveronmental Tehnol., Univ. of Cadiz, E-11510 Puerto Real Cadiz. Spain. Quality of wheat germ oil extracted by liquid and supercritical carbon dioxide JAOCS: J. Amer/Oil Chem.Soc., 2000. 77, Nr. 9/ pp.969-974.

8. Panfili G., Cincuenta L, Fratianni A., Cubadda R. (Department of Agricultural, Food, Environmental and Microbiological Science and Tehnology, University of Molise, 86100 Campobasso, Italy). Extraction of wheat germ oil by supercritical CO₂: oil and defatted cake characterization JAOCS: J.Amer. Oil Chem.Soc., 2003, 80. Nr. 2. pp. 157 -161.

9. Tokuda S., Okudera M., alt., *J. Jpn, Soc Nutr. FoodSci.*, 1984, 37, 209.

10. Козловский В.С. Биологически активные добавки из зародышей пшеницы Хранение и переработка зерна. 2005. №1, с.36 - 38.

11. Попов А.А. Повышение качества обогащенных жировых продуктов питания функционального назначения: Автореф. дис. на соиск. уч. степ. канд. техн. наук. Моск. гос. ун-т технол. и упр., Москва, 2006, 21 с., ил.. Библ. 14.